
Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States

N'dri, Konan LÉON

UFR Des Sciences Economiques et de Gestion, Université de Cocody, BPV. 43,
Abidjan, CÔTE D'IVOIRE.

Mobile: +225-0761-0329; E-mail: konanleond@yahoo.com.

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the link between financial development and economic growth in the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) economies. Using annual data on the growth rate of the per capita gross domestic product, financial development indicators and control variables over the period from 1962 to 2002, the study tests the impact of financial development on economic growth within the Zellner SUR framework. The results are as follows: 1) overall, the effect of financial development on economic growth is weak but Cote d'Ivoire enjoys the highest gain from financial development; 2) the results corroborate the findings that financial development plays a poor role in promoting economic growth in developing countries than in developed markets; 3) the study makes some recommendations to strengthen the financial structure so as to make the maximum gain from it.

JEL Classification: G10; O16; O40.

Keywords: WAEMU; Financial Development; Economic Growth; SUR.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of financial development for economic growth has been the subject of many studies in recent years. Theory suggests that a well-functioning financial market should promote investment by identifying and funding good business opportunities, mobilize savings, monitor the performance of managers, enable the trading, hedging and diversification of risk and, facilitate the exchange of goods and services. These functions result in a more efficient allocation of resources, in a more rapid accumulation of physical and human capital, and in faster technological progress, which in turn feed economic growth (Creane *et al.*, 2004).

However, a consensus has yet to be reached on this important link between financial market and economic growth. Economists disagree about the role of the financial sector as a driving force for economic growth. Three views can be identified. The first view considers that a well functioning financial market is conducive to economic growth (Schumpeter, 1911; Goldsmith, 1969; McKinnon, 1973; Shaw, 1973; Odedokun, 1998; King and Levine (1993a, 1993b). For example Schumpeter (1911), McKinnon (1973) and, King and Levine (1993a,b) showed that financial development may lead to growth in that a well-developed financial system performs several critical functions to enhance the efficiency of intermediation namely by reducing information, transaction, and monitoring costs. For the second view, finance is regarded as a relatively unimportant factor in growth (Robinson, 1952; Lucas, 1988; Stern, 1989). For example Robinson (1952) and Lucas (1988) dismiss finance as an "over-stressed" determinant of economic growth. Robinson (1952) famously argued that "where enterprise leads finance follows." From this perspective, finance does not cause growth; finance responds to changing demands from the "real sector". Finally the third view concentrates on the potential negative impact of finance on growth (Van Wijnbergen, 1983; Buffie, 1984).

Given the conflicting views cited above, it is primary an empirical question as to whether financial development spurs economic growth. The purpose of this paper is to contribute to this literature by

LÉON, Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States.

examining the relation between financial development and economic growth in the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU)¹ States. Several reasons justify the importance of this study. First, it is argued everywhere in the literature that a well-developed domestic financial sector can contribute significantly to raising the savings rate, the investment rate and, hence, transmit to economic growth (Beci and Wang, 1997). Consequently, many countries in the region have reformed their economic and financial systems to improve the efficiency of their financial intermediaries, achieve financial sector deepening, and promote growth. It is, therefore, necessary to assess the extent to which the progress achieved by these countries in their financial system has contributed to economic growth. Second, this study will enable us to uncover whether the financial sector growth nexus exhibits different characteristics from those in developed markets and within the WAEMU states. In fact, the different characteristics of the countries with respect to the banking sector can provide useful insight into the financial sector growth relationships. Third, a good understanding of the relationships between financial sector and economic growth will have important implications for policymakers. In fact, if financial sector development contributes to economic growth as postulated by theory, then policymakers should take actions to boost it. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 gives an overview of the WAEMU financial system. Section 3 describes the data. Section 4 exposes the econometric approach. Section 5 presents the empirical results and, section 6 bears on the conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE WAEMU FINANCIAL SYSTEM

The financial system of the WAEMU is mainly composed of a network of banks and financial institutions. Actually, the financing of economic activity relies essentially on the banking sector. It is therefore worthwhile to assess the contribution of the banking and financial institutions in spurring economic growth.

Table 1: Summary statistics of economic performance, financial variables and control variables

	BENIN		BF		CIV		NIGER		SEN		TOGO		WAEMU	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
GDP	3.437	3.346	3.487	3.311	4.012	5.771	1.727	6.353	2.641	4.409	3.565	6.294	3.145	5.085
GDPCH	0.797	3.275	1.194	3.219	0.414	5.417	-1.334	6.174	-0.121	4.298	0.771	6.294	0.287	4.963
LLGDP	20.012	6.997	14.461	5.480	26.537	3.577	11.339	5.390	22.672	5.301	27.680	10.610	20.450	8.854
INFL	5.498	6.803	4.755	5.598	6.520	10.011	5.150	9.067	5.051	5.590	5.603	9.854	5.429	7.983
GGCGDP	10.568	2.017	11.460	3.166	13.783	3.146	11.436	2.882	13.385	4.212	14.899	4.200	12.588	3.662
OPEN	42.125	11.385	32.083	7.827	69.024	7.516	40.063	11.737	63.414	14.131	84.471	18.261	55.197	22.203
POP	2.585	0.461	2.240	0.222	3.513	0.546	3.057	0.282	2.684	0.196	2.742	0.912	2.803	0.637
DCBGDP	14.775	8.619	8.647	4.672	31.140	11.007	10.808	5.521	29.162	13.114	18.937	9.446	18.912	12.537
DCPGDP	15.499	8.657	9.956	4.566	28.106	9.460	9.489	5.079	24.815	9.271	18.537	6.7115	17.734	10.231

Notes: Mean is the arithmetic mean and SD is the standard deviation. GDP is the gross domestic product; GDPCH is growth rate of the per capita gross domestic product; LLGDP is the ratio of liquid liability to GDP; INFL is the inflation rate; GGCGDP is the general government consumption expenditure to GDP; OPEN is the openness ratio measured as the total volume of exports plus imports as a percentage of GDP; POP is the population rate; DCBGDP is the domestic credit provided by the banking sector as percentage of GDP. DCPGDP is domestic credit to private sector as percentage of GDP.

¹ The WAEMU was set up on 10 January 1994 and comprises eight member States: Benin, Burkina-Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal and, Togo that share a common currency, the Franc of the Financial Community of Africa (CFA Fr). The CFA Fr is pegged to the Euro at a fixed rate of 1 Euro to 655.957 CFA Fr.

LÉON, Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States.

The banking system comprises seventy banks and twenty financial institutions² with 49 per cent of total assets detained by nationals and 51 per cent by foreign investors. Côte d'Ivoire and Senegal represent the bulk of banks with sixteen and ten banks respectively. Branches of foreign banks play an important role in the Union's banking system. The BNP/Paribas, SocGen, the Crédit Lyonnais, the Belgolaise, Citibank-NA, Ecobank and, the Bank of Africa dominate the Union's banking system. These seven groups control 40 per cent of credit institutions and hold 68 per cent of market share as of December 2000.

With this brief description of the characteristics of the financial system, I now take up the issue of growth in the real sector. I provide averages of rates of growth and some of the macroeconomic variables for the period 1962 through 2002 in Table 1 below. These variables have often been considered responsible for achieving high growth rate.

It appears from Table 1 that Cote d'Ivoire is the largest economy in the WAEMU. It has the highest level of growth rate per year (4.01%) followed by Togo (3.5%) and the rest of the countries with rates of growth fluctuating around 3 per cent. Most of the neighboring countries, especially those in the North of Cote d'Ivoire heavily depend on her in the areas of trade, investment and in some cases migrant employment.

Cote d'Ivoire has also the highest level of financial intermediation. The domestic credit provided by the banking sector as percentage of the gross domestic product (DCBGDP) and the domestic credit to private sector as percentage of the gross domestic product (DCPGDP) are well above the Union's average. These measures are closely followed by Senegal.

The financial depth as captured by the liquid liability provided by the banking sector as percentage of the gross domestic product (LLGDP) is more important in Cote d'Ivoire than in other countries. By and large, Table 1 reveals the wide diversity among these countries. This is an indication that despite sharing the same currency and the same monetary policy, the Union's countries exhibit differential financial development. This suggests that a study on a country basis should be appropriate.

3. THE DATA

The data used in this study are indicators of financial depth and financial development, measures of real economic growth and, control variables. The panel data includes annual observations from the World Bank's *World Development Indicator* 2004 and cover the period from 1962 to 2002. The sample consists of six (6) countries of the WAEMU members States. Benin, Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, Niger, Senegal and, Togo are considered to ensure the longest available and balanced data. Guinea Bissau and Mali were excluded for the former joined the WAEMU in 1997 and the later withdrew from the West African Monetary Union (UMOA after its French acronym) in 1962 after her independence and returned to this Union in 1984.

I take the growth rate of the per capita gross domestic product (GDP) noted in this study as GDPCH as indicator of economic growth. It is measured as the real per capita GDP (in domestic currency) to total population.

I use the ratio of liquid liability to gross domestic product (GDP) noted LLGDP as an indicator of financial depth to measure the liquid liability in the economy. Liquid liabilities equal demand deposit plus time and savings deposits. A high liquidity ratio means higher intensity of the banking system. The assumption here is that the size of the financial sector is positively associated with financial services (King and Levine, 1993a). A second measure of financial intermediation is the ratio of gross domestic savings to GDP (GDSGDP). Like the above proxy, this measure indicates the intensity of the financial intermediaries since it corresponds to more financial services and, hence more financial development. Financial development is expected to benefit from higher GDSGDP and, consequently, higher volume of investment.

² Commission Bancaire de l'UMOA, 2004, *Rapport Annuel*, UMOA, Abidjan.

LÉON, Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States.

This measure has advantages over other measures used in the literature because most of the financial development occurs in the banking sector and, moreover, they are directly linked to investment and growth.

Besides the measures of financial development and economic growth, I use four other indicators to control for other factors associated with either economic growth or financial development. The first is openness (OPEN). It is measured as the total volume of exports plus imports as a percentage of GDP (Levine et al., 2000). In theory, the effect of total trade can be either positive or negative. Trade will positively (or negatively) affect economic growth as it increases (or decreases) within the economy. The second is inflation (INFL). It is measured as the first differenced log of the consumer price index. High inflation in the economy will cause production to slow down since products are produced at higher prices. The third is the general government consumption expenditure to GDP (GGCGDP). Government expenditure may have a positive impact on economic growth because government may encourage production by increasing subsidies to producers; public spending on the economy may improve infrastructure conditions and thus improve education and living conditions. Government expenditure may also reduce economic growth due to crowding out effect on private investment and the inflationary pressure it can lead to (Allen and Ndikumana, 1998). The fourth is the population growth rate (POP) computed as the first differenced log of the population.

4. ECONOMETRIC APPROACH

Panel data econometric technique is used in this study. The framework considered in this paper builds on the Zellner (1962) Seemingly Unrelated Regression (SUR) method. Unlike multivariate regressions the SUR estimates multi-equations simultaneously while accounting for the correlated errors at the same time and, assuming that equations do not necessarily have the same predictors. Two main reasons may justify the use of this technique. First, common monetary policy in use in the UMOA zone as well as common trade policy may influence the macroeconomy and the finance of WAEMU States'. This is such that other countries will react to any event in one of these countries thereby increasing the chances of the presence of contemporaneous correlations. Second, the differential economic and financial development coupled with structural differences among the Union's countries that endogenously determine the development of financial intermediaries and economic performance would affect the variation in the coefficients of the model; as a result, the residuals variances will differ. I consider a regression with dependent variable Y_{it} and explanatory variable X_{it} :

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

The indices i and t refer to cross-section and time series with $i=1, \dots, N$ and, $t=1, \dots, T$; ε_{it} is an error term that is independently and identically distributed. The subscripts represent the country and the year respectively. Y_{it} is the growth rate of the per capita GDP in country i for the period t ; X_{it} is the vector of explanatory variables including both financial development and control variables for country i in period t ; α_i is the country specific intercept.

5. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

In order to apply the SUR method, I carry out a poolability test. The test is performed to test the null hypothesis of common intercept and slopes coefficients versus the alternative of running individual regressions for each of the cross section. An F-test is used to test the above. The critical value for the F-statistic is defined as $F((N-1)K', N(T-K'))$. N is number of groups; K' is the number of regressors in the mode and, T is the number of temporal observations. The calculated F-statistic ($F=2.13$) when LLGDP is used as indicator of financial development exceeds the critical value of $F(30,210;0.05) = 1.46$ and, the null hypothesis of a common intercept and common slope coefficients for all cross-sections is rejected thereby implying that the data should not be pooled for regression purposes. Using GDSGDP as measure of financial development also indicates that the data should not be pooled.

LÉON, Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States.

Table 2: SUR estimates of the link between Financial development and growth with llgdp as indicator of financial development.

	BENIN	BF	CIV	NIGER	SEN	TOGO
Constant	8.303 (0.015)*	0.853 (0.904)	-13.892 (0.122)	0.681 (0.955)	1.719 (0.885)	7.147 (0.129)
llgdp	0.171 (0.122)	-0.021 (0.897)	0.767 (0.013)*	-0.375 (0.174)	-0.055 (0.786)	-0.306 (0.001)*
Infl	-0.190 (0.027)*	-0.197 (0.045)*	-0.121 (0.105)	-0.263 (0.016)*	-0.149 (0.354)	0.115 (0.155)
ggcgdp	-0.517 (0.094)**	-0.341 (0.303)	-1.753 (0.000)*	0.462 (0.463)	-0.149 (0.577)	-0.556 (0.027)*
open	0.130 (0.048)*	0.228 (0.089)**	-0.042 (0.691)	0.111 (0.307)	0.116 (0.173)	0.171 (0.006)*
pop	-3.838 (0.060)*	-0.814 (0.856)	6.218 (0.000)*	-2.006 (0.728)	-1.950 (0.632)	-1.720 (0.063)*
R²	0.195	0.114	0.423	0.144	0.066	0.349

Notes: Estimates of SUR models with gdpch as dependant variable, llgdp as financial development variable and, infl, ggcgdp, open and pop as control variables. These variables are defined as in Table 1. * denotes significance at the 5%.

Table 2 and Table 3 present the SUR estimates of the link between financial development and economic growth when LLGDP and GDSGDP are used as measures of financial development respectively. Overall, the impact of financial development in both tables is weak as evidenced by the R-square ranging from 0.066 to 0.423 in Table 2 and, from 0.085 to 0.459 in Table 3. The highest R-square on Cote d'Ivoire in both tables indicates that the country gains the most from financial development. The use of LLGDP as well as GDSGDP as financial development indicators yields mixed results. LLGDP leads to positive coefficients for Benin and Cote d'Ivoire and to negative coefficients for rest of the countries whereas GDSGDP has positive coefficients on all countries. It is however worthwhile to analyze country specific results as economic indicators vary largely across countries.

LLGDP is positive and significant at the 5 per cent level in Cote d'Ivoire indicating that deposit resources of commercial banks are used to finance private domestic investments which in turn can boost economic growth. GDSGDP also exercises a positive impact on the growth of Cote d'Ivoire, Niger and Togo as evidenced by the positive and significant coefficients at the 5 per cent level. Mobilized savings in those countries are thus used to finance private investment. Though the expected positive signs on LLGDP for Benin, and on GDSGDP for Benin, Burkina Faso and Senegal are met, they are not significant. This implies that mobilized savings as well as deposit resources from commercial banks are either low or not sufficient enough to spur economic growth in these countries. Benin's case may be due to the fact that she adopted socialism as a mean of economic development over the period from 1974 to 1990.

Table 2 and Table 3 show that control variables exhibit almost similar effects. As expected, inflation has an adverse impact in all countries except in Togo. The negative impact is significant at the 5 per cent level for Benin, Burkina Faso and Niger (Table 2) and, for Benin, Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire and, Niger (Table 3). This implies that the existence of high inflation will lead to more conservative investment strategies that would result in lower levels of investments and economic growth. The results on government expenditure are negative and significant at the 10 per cent level for Benin and; at the 5 per cent level for Cote d'Ivoire and Togo (Table 2) and, for Togo (Table 3) thereby indicating that large government spending may crowd out private investment and reduce economic growth. Openness to trade has a positive and significant impact on economic growth at the 10 per cent level for Burkina Faso and, at the 5 per cent level for Benin and Togo (Table 2) and, for Benin and Burkina Faso (Table 3). This effect may result largely from export of agricultural product from these countries. Finally, the coefficients on population are negative and significant at the 5 per cent level for Benin and Togo in Table 2 and, for Togo in Table 3

LÉON, Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States.

suggesting that population growth is not sufficient enough to spur economic growth. Population growth is meanwhile more meaningful for Cote d'Ivoire since its coefficient is positive and significant at the 5 per cent level.

Table 3: SUR estimates of the link between Financial development and growth with gdsgdp as indicator of financial development.

	BENIN	BF	CIV	NIGER	SEN	TOGO
Constant	5.610 (0.076)**	0.392 (0.952)	-0.292 (0.973)	-9.504 (0.446)	-3.150 (0.784)	10.158 (0.033)
gdsgdp	0.104 (0.447)	0.083 (0.417)	0.604 (0.002)*	0.488 (0.019)*	0.141 (0.342)	0.236 (0.006)*
Infl	-0.181 (0.047)*	-0.185 (0.058)*	-0.128 (0.078)**	-0.224 (0.028)*	-0.134 (0.402)	0.014 (0.872)
ggcgdp	-0.483 (0.129)	-0.432 (0.171)	-0.114 (0.768)	-0.277 (0.579)	-0.097 (0.693)	-0.741 (0.004)*
open	0.153 (0.029)*	0.235 (0.077)**	-0.165 (0.167)	-0.064 (0.521)	0.091 (0.261)	0.045 (0.443)
pop	-2.055 (0.245)	-0.482 (0.909)	0.180 (0.937)	4.094 (0.481)	-0.614 (0.876)	-2.181 (0.019)*
R²	0.160	0.128	0.459	0.211	0.085	0.316

Notes: Estimates of SUR models with *gdgdp* as dependant variable, *gdsgdp* as financial development variable and, *infl*, *ggcgdp*, *open* and *pop* as control variables. These variables are defined as in Table 1. * and ** denote significance at the 5% and 10% respectively.

6. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper has examined the link between financial development and economic growth in the WAEMU economies. Using annual data on economic growth, financial development and control variables, the study applies the Zellner SUR method to assess the impact of financial development on economic growth. The study shows that Cote d'Ivoire gains the most from financial development and, confirms the findings that financial development contributes more to growth in mature markets than in developing countries. Meanwhile, the study shows that overall, the effect of financial development on economic growth is weak. In order to make the maximum gains from financial development, the study calls for steps toward strengthening the weak financial system, and resolving the institutional and structural problems within the WAEMU economies. For instance, attention may focus on the following: Building the domestic entrepreneurial capacity; Strengthening the legal system and bank supervision; Addressing issues on property rights and titles. This will enable individuals to provide the collateral needed to access credits from banks; Opening a section for small and medium size enterprises at the regional stock market (BRVM after its French acronym). This will enable them to raise more money at lower cost.

REFERENCES

- Allen, D. S. and Ndikumana, L. (1998), Financial Intermediation and Economic Growth in Southern Africa, *Working Paper Series, 1998-004, Economics*, the Federal Reserve Bank of ST. Louis, 58 (1): 195-209.
- Becsi, Z. and Wang, P. (1997), Financial development and growth, *Economic Review*, Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, Issue Q4: 46-62.
- Buffie, E. F. (1984), Financial Repression, the New Structuralists, and Stabilization Policy in Semi-Industrialized Economics, *Journal of Development Economics*, 14: 305-22.
- Commission Bancaire de l'UMOA (2004), *Rapport Annuel*, UMOA, Abidjan.

LÉON, Financial Development and Economic Growth in the WAEMU States.

Creane, S., Goyal, R., Mobarak, M. A., and Sab, R. (2004), Financial Sector Development in the Middle East and North Africa, *IMF Working Paper 04/201*.

Goldsmith, R. W. (1969), *Financial Structure and Development*, New Haven, C.T.: Yale University Press.

Greenwood, J. and Jovanovic, B. (1990), Financial Development, Growth, and the Distribution of Income, *Journal of Political Economy*, 98: 1076-1107.

King, R. G and Levine, R. (1993a), Finance and Growth: Schumpeter might be Right, *Quarterly Journal of Monetary Economics*, 108: 717-38.

King, R. G. and Levine, R. (1993b), Finance, Entrepreneurship, and Growth, *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 32: 513-42.

Levine, R., Loayza, N., and Beck, T. (2000), Financial Intermediation and Economic Growth: Causality and Causes, *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 46: 31-77.

Lucas, R. E. Jr. (1988), On the Mechanics of Economic Development, *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22: 3-42.

Mckinnon, R. I. (1973), *Money and Capital in Economic Development*, Washington, D. C.: Brooking Institution.

Odedokun, M. O. (1998), Financial Intermediation and Economic Growth in Developing Countries, *Journal of Economic Studies*, 25: 203-24.

Robinson, J. (1952), *the Generalization of the General Theory, the Rate of Interest and Other Essays*, McMillan, London.

Schumpeter, J. A. (1911), *the Theory of Economic Development*, Cambridge, Mass: Harvard University Press.

Shaw, E. S. (1973), *Financial Deepening in Economic Development*, Cambridge, M.A.: Havard University Press.

Stern, N. (1989), the Economics of Development: a Survey, *The Economic Journal*, 100: 597-685.

Van Wijnbergen, S. (1983), Credit Policy, Inflation, and Growth in a Financially Repressed Economy, *Journal of Development Economics*, 13: 45-65.

Zellner, A. (1962), an Efficient Method of Estimating Seemingly Unrelated Regressions and Tests of Aggregation Bias, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 57: 500-9.